

CHEMICAL SCIENCES

DETERMINATION OF THE CHEMICAL COMPOSITION OF AGRICULTURAL SOILS

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ABSTRACT

The intensity of contamination of agricultural soils with heavy metals in the city of Uman was investigated. It was established that the content of heavy metals in the soil samples taken in the city of Uman, Cherkasy region, ranged from: Cu – 3.8 – 4.0 mg/kg; Zn – 4.3 – 4.8 mg/kg; Pb - 3.9 - 4.3 mg/kg. None of the heavy metals exceeded the maximum permissible standards, which makes it possible to consider these soils completely safe for growing agricultural crops.

Keywords: soils, heavy metals, agricultural land, chemical composition.

Formulation of the problem. The human population is growing continuously at a rate of about one billion per decade. The current level of production of agricultural products cannot satisfy the need for food in sufficient quantity. The possibilities of extensive expansion of production through exploitation of new lands have been exhausted. In addition, as a result of urbanization, uncultivable land is used for the development of settlements. Calculations by FAO experts show that to solve the world food problem, a continuous increase in the productivity of the main agricultural crops is necessary in the next 30 years for wheat and rice by 1.2% annually, maize by 1.5% annually, sugar beet and sugarcane by 1, 8% annually.

At the same time, with a general shortage of land resources, due to errors in the management of agricultural production processes, the area of degraded agricultural lands due to erosion, salinization and waterlogging is growing at a rate of approximately 10 million hectares per year. In Ukraine, the poor management of agricultural production has led to the fact that every year due to pollution, the amount of eroded land in Ukraine increases by 80-90 thousand hectares.

Analysis of recent research and publications.

The current state of soils is a concern of the entire civilized world. The increase in the area of degraded soils, the deterioration of their quality condition forces the world community to raise the issue of protection and rational use of soil resources at the highest political level. Soil is one of the important environments that is subject to significant anthropogenic influence. Accumulation of toxic substances in the soil leads to migration to plants, and their products and subsequently with food products to the human body.

Heavy metals are one of the most toxic soil pollutants. They can enter the soil with mineral fertilizers, limestone materials, pesticides, exhaust gases of vehicles, with emissions of industrial enterprises. Chemical pollution of soils used in agriculture is divided into pollution by heavy metals, pesticide residues, radionuclides and acid precipitation [1].

Heavy metals are metals such as cadmium, mercury, and lead that are 2.0-3.7 times heavier than iron by atomic weight and 1.1-1.7 times heavier than iron. Today, heavy metals also include chromium, cobalt,

nickel, copper, zinc, arsenic, selenium, silver, cadmium, mercury, thallium and lead, some compounds of which can be quite toxic. The main danger of poisoning by heavy metals threatens agricultural animals that feed on vegetative terrestrial parts of plants, which can be contaminated both by aerial and soil means [2,3].

The content of cadmium in food products over the last century has a tendency to increase, which is the result of environmental pollution. The accumulation of cadmium in the body of humans and animals is associated with its very slow elimination. The use of some types of mineral fertilizers for agricultural plants, as well as the liming of small doses of acidic soils for cereal grain crops contribute to the entry of cadmium into grain and straw [4,5].

Mercury is a serious danger to human health. It occurs in three forms: in the form of inorganic salts and in the form of organic compounds, which are more often found in the environment, since metallic mercury can be transformed into organic alkaline compounds under the action of microorganisms. Methylmercury is the most widespread in the human habitat [6-8].

A third metal that poses a health hazard and is common in agricultural landscapes is lead. The main way of contamination of agricultural plants and soils in this case is aerial. The daily intake of lead with human food is about 35 µg. Plant pollution occurs mainly mechanically as a result of the diffusion of lead from contaminated soil into tubers and root crops, as well as due to the deposition of lead compounds from the atmosphere on the surface of stems, leaves and fruits - mainly in the form of oxides [9-12].

Research methodology. The research was conducted in September 2020 - 2023. Soil samples were taken in the city Uman on a square plot measuring 10 × 10 meters using the "envelope" method. Samples were taken in the morning in dry weather at a depth of 25 cm weighing 1 kg. After sampling, the samples were dried to an air-dry state in a drying cabinet with a temperature regulator.

Soil analysis was carried out at Pavlo Tychyna Uman State Pedagogical University according to DSTU 4770. 1-9: 2007. The method is based on extracting the mobile form of copper, zinc and lead ions from the soil with an acetate-ammonium buffer solution with

a pH of 4.8. At the same time, part of exchangeable cations passes into the solution, hydrolysis of compounds occurs, acetate or ammonium complex compounds are formed. Due to the high buffer capacity of this solution, the reaction of the environment during the removal of heavy metals from various soils remains stable. Determination on a spectrophotometer after atomization of the sample in an air-acetylene flame is based on the property of atoms in the ground state to absorb light of defined and specific wavelengths for each type of atom. The mass concentration of copper, zinc and lead in the samples (c), in milligrams per kilogram, is calculated by the formula:

$$c = c_{sp} \frac{V \cdot 1000}{1000 \cdot m},$$

where C_{rp} is the mass concentration of copper, zinc, and lead, respectively, in the extract, obtained according to the calibration curve, mg/dm^3 ; V – volume of acetate-ammonium buffer solution for sample preparation, cm^3 ; 1000 is the conversion factor of g into kg; 1000 is the coefficient of conversion of cm^3 into 1 dm^3 ; m is the weight of the soil sample, g.

Fig. 1 Content of heavy metals in agricultural soils in 2020-2023.

The same situation is observed with regard to zinc content, which increased by 0.5 mg/kg from 2020 to 2023. One of the main ways zinc enters the plant is the absorption of chemical compounds of these metals (salts, hydroxides) by the roots. A feature of zinc pollution is the slow self-cleaning of soils, which negatively affects the yield of agricultural crops. The content of lead in the soil in 2023 was lower by 0.4 mg/kg compared to 2020.

The zinc content in the soil helps plants better resist high temperatures and various fungal diseases. In addition, zinc contributes to the acceleration of various chemical processes in plants. Due to the lack of zinc in the soil, deformation of the leaves and the plant itself occurs, growth slows down. Fertilizing the soil with

The purpose of the work there is coverage of issues related to soil contamination with heavy metals and research on the content of macroelements in agricultural soils.

Results. The results of the study showed a general tendency to increase the copper content over the years, which ranged from 3.8 to 4.0 mg/kg.

An increase in the concentration of copper in the soil can lead to significant poisoning of the plant organism. Further accumulation of copper along the food chain is a potential threat to human and animal health.

The movement of copper and its entry into plants are reduced due to liming of soils, binding of copper in the form of organic compounds and fixing with soil humus. Soil microorganisms play an important role in fixing copper. A portion of soil copper is strongly associated with soil humic acids and in this form it is unassimilable for plants. Copper deficiency for plants is more pronounced on sandy and peaty soils. At the same time, the availability of copper for plants on acidic soils is higher than on soils with a neutral and alkaline reaction of the environment.

zinc helps restore plant growth. Such plants as potatoes, beets, hops, and perennial legumes react most strongly to zinc deficiency.

Excessive zinc content in the soil, in turn, leads to negative consequences.

Macronutrients are the basis of the nutrition of agricultural crops, the main ones of which are phosphorus, nitrogen and potassium.

The phosphorus content in the soil varied between 64.3-65 mg/kg, which is positive for plant life. Phosphorus deficiency manifests itself in the depression of the plant, late flowering and stunted growth. It is not possible to compensate for the deficiency of this element by further feeding, so its presence in the soil is necessary.

Fig. 2 The content of macroelements in agricultural soils in 2020-2023.

All agricultural crops feel the greatest need for nitrogen. It is nitrogen that affects the rate of plant growth, the formation of strong stems, and the reduction of the rate of aging. The nitrogen content in the studied samples ranged from 118 to 120 mg/kg. In 2023, this indicator was the highest.

Potassium in plants is mainly located in the cytoplasm, it is easily washed away by rains and has the ability to move from old leaves to young ones, ensuring its functions: protection from drought, participation in metabolic processes and activation of enzyme activity. The potassium content in the soil ranged from 94.5 to 95.8 mg/kg, which is sufficient for efficient farming.

Conclusions. It was established that the content of heavy metals in the agricultural soil samples taken in the city of Uman, Cherkasy region, ranged from: Cu – 3.8 – 4.0 mg/kg; Zn – 4.3 – 4.8 mg/kg; Pb - 3.9 - 4.3 mg/kg. None of the heavy metals exceeded the maximum permissible standards, which makes it possible to consider these soils completely safe for growing agricultural crops. The phosphorus content in the soil varied between 64.3-65 mg/kg; nitrogen in the range of 118-120 mg/kg; potassium 94.5-95.8 mg/kg. In general, the ecological condition of the studied soils is satisfactory.

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